

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

Project Management Handbook

Deliverable 8.1

WP8. Management and Coordination

Project title

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ABBREVIATIONS

CA	:	Consortium Agreement
DoA	:	Description of Action
GA	:	General Assembly
IAB	:	International Advisory Board
MST	:	Project Management Support Team
OG	:	Operational Group
PC	:	Project Coordinator
PCT	:	Project Coordination Team
PO	:	Project Office
TC	:	Technical Committee
DEM	:	Dissemination and Exploitation Manager

PARTNERS SHORT NAMES

AUA - AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

UNIBO – UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

ATB - AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING AND BIOECONOMY

EV ILVO - AGRICULTURAL AND FISHERIES RESEARCH

UGENT - GHENT UNIVERSITY

CERTH - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY-HELLAS

AU - AARHUS UNIVERSITY

LVAT - LEHR- UND VERSUCHSANSTALT FÜR TIERZUCHT UND TIERHALTUNG GROß KREUTZ E.V.

PSYCTOTHERM - G. LIGEROS & SIA OE

PLEGMA LABS- PLEGMA LABS TECHNOLOGIKES LYSEIS ANONYMOS ETAIRIA

CRMT SAS - CENTRE DE RECHERCHES EN MACHINES THERMIQUES

TERRA - TERRA ENERGY

MG SUSTAINABLE - MG SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING AB

CETRI - CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH & INNOVATION LTD

GOLINELLI - GOLINELLI GIULIO

EAAP - FEDERAZIONE EUROPEA PER LA ZOOTECNICA

EUREC - EUREC EESV

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The purpose of this document is to ensure that Project Management and Quality Assurance are in accordance with the contractual requirements for monitoring the project. This document will enable the Consortium and the Commission to have a clear view of project timeline, tasks and resources distribution. The overall project team organization and responsibilities are described as well as the quality management process and the risk management.

The structure of the document is as follows: Project description is included within section 2, where the main objectives and project participants are presented. In section 3, information on work plan, management structure, reporting, project documentation, website, project image and collaboration tools have been included. Finally, section 4 describes risk management and section 5 concludes the document.

D8.1: Project Management Handbook is a living document, aiming at reflecting all changes within the project's lifetime.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The establishment of adequate management procedures are fundamental for the execution of projects like RES4LIVE, where a quite large number of tasks is interconnected, and each partner needs to perform different activities in order to meet common goals. In this document, the management handbook for RES4LIVE project is presented. Its purpose was to ensure that project management is in accordance with contractual requirements and contribute to the success of the joint work.

Project description has been included within section 2. RES4LIVE main objectives and project participants are presented. In section 3, information on work plan, management structure, reporting, project documentation, website and project image, and collaboration tools have been included. Finally, section 4 describes risk management and section 5 concludes the document.

Some of the content in this document is already part of the Description of Action (DoA) in the Grant Agreement. However, the DoA is a document no longer possible to be updated. The Project Management Handbook (D8.1) is a living document, aiming at reflecting all changes within the project's lifetime. It is expected that this deliverable is used as reference for all project partners.

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2 PROJECT DESCRIPTION

In this section there is a short description of the RES4LIVE project. If one of the partners requires more detailed information on the implementation of the project, there is also access to Description of Action (DoA).

2.1 Main Objectives

The main objective of RES4LIVE is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective and case-sensitive Renewable Energy Sources (RES) solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming. To that end, RES4LIVE will adapt and test promising RES technologies in energy-intensive livestock farming (swine, dairy and poultry) for greatly reducing the fossil energy that is the main source to cover the energy demand. Dedicated, optimal designs combined with energy efficiency and other solutions are proposed, demonstrated in 4 pilot farms and evaluated technically, economically, environmentally, and socially. The overall objective is to provide advanced and cost-effective technologies to the livestock sector that ensure the sustainability of the farms' operation, and the superior thermal comfort of the animals for increased productivity with minimum climate change impact.

RES4LIVE project has a series of specific objectives to be achieved in order to successfully complete this project.

Objective 1: RES and machinery adaptation, and other technologies selection

RES4LIVE will consider different RES technologies and appropriate energy efficiency measures, and practices together with machinery. Their diverse energy consuming divisions and needs require different key technologies to be adapted so that to perfectly fit livestock farming. The objectives of the key technologies are the following:

- Photovoltaic/Thermal (PVT) technology for both heat and electricity production
- Heat pump for precise indoor environment at all thermal modes (heating, cooling, dehumidification)
- Biomethane production from biogas (derived from manure) upgraded for either Combined Heat and Power (CHP) or fuel for farm tractors
- Tractor retrofitting, in order to be fuelled with biomethane produced on-site, properly adapting the necessary auxiliaries as well
- RES systems, energy efficiency solutions and practices

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Objective 2: Pilot systems design, installation and testing

The adapted-adopted RES and energy efficiency measures and technologies identified will be inventoried and used in advanced simulation and optimization tools for the design of specific systems to be installed in the pilot livestock farms. These tools are supported with energy control methodologies based on innovative practices applied in domestic buildings. The relevant specific objectives are:

- Development of numerical methodologies and tools conducting dynamic simulations considering both energy demand and supply from different sources
- Development of smart energy control techniques for optimized livestock buildings environment
- Designing and preparing all required components for the 4 pilot farms
- Testing and demonstrating the pilot systems in the farms for a period of 12 months

Objective 3: Multi-level Assessment

A thorough evaluation and assessment will be conducted, with the following specific objectives:

- Technical assessment. The test data will be used to identify the energy share covered by RES in conjunction with the fossil energy share and the reduction of primary energy consumption, once applying energy efficiency measures. This process will assess the energy use status in the 3 farm types, aiming for a 100% replacement of fossil energy in all farms
- Environmental and economic assessment. An extended Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach integrated with economic assessment criteria will be conducted and the tangible positive results on the economic viability of the farms and the environmental impact will be derived
- Social assessment. A social LCA approach dedicated to livestock farms will be developed, including socio-economic indicators. This approach will be fine-tuned based on the feedback of the end-users
- Validation of numerical tools. Based on the test data, the validation of the numerical tools will target a deviation between predictions and read data on an annual basis lower than 15%. This process will enable the extended use of the tools for a variety of farm sizes and technologies included, and finally used for replicability purposes and case studies analysis for maximizing the project impact

Objective 4: Replicability and impact generation

RES4LIVE includes various tasks aiming at the replicability enhancement and sustainability of solutions. These will increase the project's impact towards the market uptake of the proposed technologies and practices. The relevant specific objectives are given next:

- Replicability of solutions. To strengthen project's impact, replicability of the RES systems is favoured through the implementation of 15 case studies, covering: (1) diverse farm types other than the pilot ones, (2) different farm sizes, and (3) various geographical locations to account

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for different heating/cooling needs. The validated tools will be used to conduct this analysis with the final aim to identify the fossil fuel reduction and other key environmental and cost parameters.

- Interaction with key stakeholders. RES4LIVE will liaise with over 200 stakeholders (e.g. technology providers, installers, farmers and local farm associations) to promote the actual positive results of the proposed solutions. The aim is to strengthen the co-design processes for energy smart livestock farms so that the project activities are always kept in-line with the market needs.
- Clustering formation. To further increase the impact, the RES4LIVE will join forces with more than 10 other projects and initiatives so that to form clusters for enhancing the awareness of multiple stakeholders; starting from the common dissemination activities and up to the recommendations relevant to policy.
- Roll-out a comprehensive communication, dissemination and exploitation plan, sharing the project insights and results with various stakeholders through exhibitions, site visits, conferences, and handbooks. The overall aim is to tailor strategies for societal awareness and engagement for a variety of groups.

2.2 Participants

The participating entities in RES4LIVE project are shown in Table 1:

Partners Details			
No.	INSTITUTION NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
1	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON (Agricultural University of Athens)	AUA	Greece
2	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA (University of Bologna)	UNIBO	Italy
3	LEIBNIZ INSTITUT FUER AGRARTECHNIK UND BIOOEKONOMIE E.V. (Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Engineering and Bio- economy e.V.)	ATB	Germany
4	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK (Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food)	EV ILVO	Belgium
5	UNIVERSITEIT GENT (Ghent University)	UGENT	Belgium

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6	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS (Centre for Research and Technology - Hellas)	CERTH	Greece
7	AARHUS UNIVERSITET (Aarhus University)	AU	Denmark
8	LEHR- UND VERSUCHSANSTALT FUER TIERZUCHT UND TIERHALTUNG (LVAT) E.V.	LVAT	Germany
9	G. LIGEROS & SIA OE	PSYCTOTHERM	Greece
10	PLEGMA LABS TECHNOLOGIKES LYSEIS ANONYMOS ETAIRIA	PLEGMA LABS	Greece
11	CRMT SAS - CENTRE DE RECHERCHES EN MACHINES THERMIQUES	CRMT SAS	France
12	TERRA ENERGY	TERRA	Belgium
13	MG SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERING AB	MG	Sweden
14	CENTER FOR TECHNOLOGY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION LTD	CETRI	Cyprus
15	GOLINELLI GIULIO	GOLINELLI	Italy
16	FEDERAZIONE EUROPEA DI ZOOTECNICA (European Federation of Animal Science)	EAAP	Italy
17	EUREC EESV (The Association of European Renewable Energy Research Centers)	EUREC	Belgium

Table 1: Partners Details

Each of these partners (Universities, Research Institutes and SMEs) is vital for the successful completion of the project due to their expertise. More particularly, a brief description of the partners' expertise and their responsibilities in the project are given in the Table below.

Partners Expertise and Responsibilities		
No.	SHORT NAME	EXPERTISE & RESPONSIBILITIES
1	AUA	AUA will act as RES4LIVE project coordinator (WP8 Leader) and WP5 leader, where the technical, economic and environmental evaluation of RES technologies applied in the 4 pilot farms will be executed. AUA will also be responsible to integrate the proposed RES solutions in the pilot poultry farm in its premises, within WP4. Finally, AUA will be involved in clustering with other relative EU projects and initiatives to

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		promote the work of RES4LIVE and receive best practices from mature actors (WP6) and conduct continuous dissemination activities.
2	UNIBO	UNIBO will be scientific partner mainly supporting the realization, testing and assessing the installed RES technologies in the pilot Golinelli farm. Of significance is also its involvement in WP5 technical, socio-economic and environmental assessment, related to the Golinelli farm application. UNIBO will also have an active role in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders. It should be noted that UNIBO is also involved in dissemination and communication activities.
3	ATB	ATB will lead WP4, where tasks include integration, testing and monitoring of RES solutions in experimental and commercial farms and will also work in close collaboration with the experimental farm of LVAT for the German case study. ATB will be active in WP1, 2 and 3, so that the implementation phase in the pilot farms will be executed in the optimum way, and in the technical, socio economic and environmental assessment, related to the LVAT farm application. ATB will also participate actively in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.
4	EV ILVO	EV ILVO will take active role in WP1, 2 and 3 in order to assist in preparing the activities of WP4, where its experimental farm will be act as a pilot. EV ILVO will be also Task leader in T3.2, which is directly connected to its expertise and will assist the consortium to show the tangible results on animal welfare. In addition, EV ILVO will be active in the technical, socio-economic and environmental assessment, related to providing data from its experimental farm and will participate actively in the clustering activities, co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.
5	UGENT	UGENT is the WP2 leader and will lead the tasks related to thermal systems and processes optimization of heat pumps design, in close collaboration with EV ILVO and AUA. In addition, UGENT will assist on the realization of the implementation phase in the EV ILVO experimental farm, and will also be active in the technical, socio-economic and environmental assessment, related to the EV ILVO farm application. Finally, UGENT will participate actively in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.
6	CERTH	CERTH will be in charge of WP3 about Livestock farm energy flows assessment, smart control and simulation, where will mainly focus on the assessment of on-farm energy demand and available renewable energy potential in EU agriculture with specific interest on the livestock subsector (iBO) and the development of a farm-specific numerical platform for energy simulations and operations optimization for calculating energy and resources flows (CPERI). CERTH will be in close collaboration with CRMT during Task 1.2 and will also participate in Task 4.4. Regarding the

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		technical and environmental assessment of the combined solutions, CERTH will use the expertise of both Institutes in LCA in WP5, while it will participate in WP6 leading Task 6.2. Finally, CERTH will be active in dissemination and communication of all activities in order to open RES4LIVE in the public.
7	AU	AU will have a significant role in WP3. Primarily, AU will assist CERTH with the identification of the existing situation in European livestock sector, while will participate in the review of the optimum thermal conditions for the different species for animal welfare achievement. AU main contribution will be in the numerical platform formulation using its large experience on precision livestock technologies and indoor smart control. Finally, AU will participate actively in the clustering activities and the co creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.
8	LVAT	LVAT will be involved in tasks in WP4 such as integration, testing, monitoring and assessment of RES solutions in its experimental farm. The work will be done in close collaboration with ATB. LVAT will also contribute in WP1, 2 and 3 so to obtain the most appropriate technologies to be fitted in its pilot farm. Finally, LVAT will participate actively in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.
9	PSYCTOTHERM	Having that relevant experience, PSYCTO will lead WP1 will also manufacture a modular heat pump for livestock buildings to be integrated in the pilot farms, where PSYCTO will participate actively for the correct installation (WP4). PSYCTO will also assist on WP2, and actively participate in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.
10	PLEGMA LABS	PLEGMA will be mainly involved to develop the control and automation components for the RES4LIVE project in WP3, being responsible for the installation of the different sensors and the development of the different components for smart control on the different pilots. To do so, PLEGMA will participate in WP1, 2 and 4, so that the control is correctly designed and implemented in the pilot farms and also participate actively in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.
11	CRMT SAS	CRMT will mainly participate in WP1, in order to lead the conversion of the Diesel agricultural tractor engine to operate with biomethane. After the completion of the tractor conversion, CRMT will participate in WP4 for implementing this tractor in the farm and measure its performance and will assist on giving the appropriate data for conducting the technical, economic, environmental and social analysis of this intervention. Finally, CRMT will participate actively in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.

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12	TERRA	TERRA ENERGY will participate mainly in WP3 and more particularly will be in charge of all activities related to the BTES fields and will assist on testing in the case study of Italian farm (WP4). In order to have a clear view of the integrated solutions, TERRA ENERGY will also participate in WP1 and 3. Finally, TERRA ENERGY will participate actively in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders (WP6) and in dissemination and communication activities (WP7).
13	MG	MG will have a significant role in WP1, envisioning and re-designing a PVT collector and design two systems to fit specifically for the RES4Live project having in mind applicability to livestock farming conditions in general. MG will design and install PVT solar systems (WP4). MG will work on best practices on energy management, by developing innovative cost-effective solutions integrating RES in farming by means of harvesting efficiently solar energy. MG will also participate in WP2 and WP5 to assist the optimum results from the PVT installation.
14	CETRI	CETRI is WP7 leader thus leading the project's dissemination, exploitation and communication activities. Moreover, the company will be involved in and the technical, economic, environmental and social assessment of the integrated technologies (WP5) and the clustering/co-creation activities (WP6).
15	GOLINELLI	Golinelli Farm participates in all WPs of the project, aiming in the best possible integration of the proposed solutions in the specific commercial farm. Golinelli represents a pilot case therefore it will be mainly involved in WP4. Finally, Golinelli will participate actively in the clustering activities and the co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities.
16	EAAP	EAAP will participate in the project's dissemination, exploitation and communication activities (WP7). Moreover, the association will be involved in and the technical, economic, environmental and social assessment of the integrated technologies (WP5) and the clustering/co-creation activities (WP6) and lead this WP.
17	EUREC	EUREC will deal with the project's dissemination, exploitation and communication activities (WP7). Moreover, the association will be involved in and the technical, economic, environmental and social assessment of the integrated technologies (WP5) and the clustering/co-creation activities (WP6).

Table 2: Partners Expertise and Responsibilities

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All partners will participate actively in the clustering activities (WP6) and the co-creation with stakeholders and in dissemination and communication activities (WP7). In Figure 1, it can be seen the geographical distribution of the RES4LIVE partners.

Figure 1: RES4LIVE Geographical Distribution

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3 PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Work Plan

Detailed work plan and WP description is included in the DoA. An overview focused on implementation details is presented in this section. RES4LIVE project is divided into 8 WPs, as can be seen in Table 3 that includes for each WP assigned leader, person-month allocation and duration.

Work Packages (WP) Breakdown and Details					
WP No.	WP TITLE	WP LEADER	PERSON-MONTHS	START MONTH	END MONTH
1	Adaptation of innovative RES technologies for livestock farms	PSYCTOTHERM	143.70	1	21
2	Market available RES and energy efficiency solutions, machinery and practices for livestock farms	UGENT	77.00	7	21
3	Livestock farm energy flows assessment, smart control and simulation	CERTH	114.00	7	30
4	Implementation and testing of the solutions in pilot farms	ATB	161.50	22	45
5	Technical, socio-economic and environmental assessment	AUA	100.50	37	48
6	Clustering through stakeholders engagement	EAAP	61.00	13	48
7	Dissemination - Communication - Exploitation	CERTI	67.00	1	48
8	Management and Coordination	AUA	45	1	48
9	Ethics Requirements	AUA	N/A	1	48
			769.70		

Table 3: Work Packages (WP) Breakdown and Details

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To achieve all specific objectives of RES4LIVE towards de-fossilising industrial livestock farming 8 Work Packages (WPs) will undertake the required actions, as shown in the Pert chart of Fig. 3.1. The timing of the different work-packages and their components is shown in the Gantt chart of Fig. 3.2.

The work starts with WP1 which is focused on the adaptation of key RES technologies namely PVT, heat pump, biomethane upgrading and tractor retrofitting for biomethane fuelling. The partners with the relevant expertise (MG, PSYCTO, and CRMT respectively) in collaboration with livestock and energy experts from research organizations will undertake the work and provide close to the market solutions for livestock farms.

At the same time, WP2 deals with the investigation, identification and adaptation of other RES and energy efficiency technologies, measures and practices, which can be effectively integrated in the livestock farms together with the adapted ones in WP1. This WP is foreseen to start at month 7 so that to have available some first data from the adaptation work of WP1, while been finalized along with WP1 so that all solutions to be ready for systems design (WP 4).

Based on the results of WPs 1-2, WP3 focuses on assessing the RES potential and energy consumption in livestock farms. A key parameter is the estimation of energy consumption, as a function of animals' thermal comfort that will be considered for different species. A dedicated task concerns the creation of a numerical platform, capable to simulate and optimise RES integrated systems of livestock farms, determining the essential design parameters. This platform will be coupled with the smart energy control, making it possible to proceed with actual pilot installations. WP3 is foreseen to start at month 7 so that to incorporate some necessary first data from WP1.

Then, the selected technologies, measures and practices will be implemented in WP4 that concerns the detailed design, installation, testing and monitoring of these integrated systems in the 4 pilot farms. The systems will be a combination of adapted technologies and other solutions, based on the availability of RES and animals' species needs and having as final decision aspect the technical and economic feasibility of interventions. This WP starts just after both adapted and market available RES and energy efficiency technologies are developed and specified (WP1 and WP2 respectively).

Based on real measurements from the integrated systems installed in the selected pilot livestock farms, WP5 will assess their technical, economic, social and environmental impact. A feedback loop to WP3 is foreseen to validate the numerical platform from the experimental results derived from the testing period.

The series of implementation steps will be based on co-design processes with relevant stakeholders to use their experience, needs and ideas on designing and using the integrated systems in the livestock farms as a part of WP6. Clustering with other projects and relative associations and unions will complement this to ensure the maximum impact on the European livestock sector. Finally, the project potential will be demonstrated through a series of case studies in livestock farms in various farm types and EU climates.

All project activities will be disseminated and communicated thoroughly within WP7 combined with an extensive market analysis of such systems as well as the elaboration of exploitation plan and IPR management.

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Finally, WP8 concerns actions for the effective coordination and management of the project and WP9 deals with ethics. The interrelationship between the RES4LIVE WPs is the key element of success for this project (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Work Packages (WPs) Interrelation

Each WP has been divided into tasks, aiming at more specific technical aspects (see DoA for details on tasks). The outputs of the tasks are included in the deliverables. Workload within the tasks and the WPs is organized with the clear objective of providing adequate deliverables, with the expected content, to fulfil project expectations. The following Table presents the list of deliverables that have been defined for RES4LIVE project.

List of Deliverables (D)						
DELIVERABLE No.	DELIVERABLE TITLE	WP No.	LEAD BENEFICIARY	TYPE	DISSEMINATION LEVEL	DUE DATE (in months)
D1.1	Upgrading manure biogas to biomethane	WP1	ATB	Demonstrator	CO	21
D1.2	The adapted farm tractor fuelled by biomethane	WP1	CRMT SAS	Demonstrator	CO	21
D1.3	The adapted flexible heat pump	WP1	PSYCTOTHERM	Demonstrator	CO	21

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D1.4	The developed PVT system designs dedicated for livestock farms	WP1	MG	Report	CO	21
D2.1	Inventory of market available RES technologies, machinery and energy efficiency solutions, and practices	WP2	AU	Report	PU	21
D2.2	Integration schemes of RES4LIVE adapted technologies with commercial solutions	WP2	UGENT	Report	PU	21
D3.1	Report on the analysis of energy demand/consumption and RES availability in typical livestock farms	WP3	CERTH	Report	PU	12
D3.2	Thermal comfort assessment of livestock and impact on production	WP3	EV ILVO	Report	CO	12
D3.3	Development of livestock farm-specific smart energy control	WP3	PLEGMA LABS	Other	CO	27
D3.4	Development of livestock farm-specific numerical platform	WP3	CERTH	Other	CO	30
D4.1	Design of integrated systems in pilot farms	WP4	AUA	Demonstrator	CO	28
D4.2	The installed pilot systems	WP4	UNIBO	Demonstrator	PU	33
D4.3	Report with the results obtained on energy and production	WP4	ATB	Report	PU	45

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	performances of RES and energy efficiency solutions					
D5.1	Technical assessment and validation of the numerical platform	WP5	CERTH	Report	PU	48
D5.2	Economic assessment report	WP5	AUA	Report	PU	48
D5.3	Environmental assessment report	WP5	AUA	Report	PU	48
D5.4	Social assessment report	WP5	CETRI	Report	PU	48
D6.1	Report on clustering activities	WP6	CETRI	Report	PU	48
D6.2	Report on policy recommendations	WP6	EUREC	Report	PU	48
D6.3	Report on co-design process	WP6	EAAP	Report	PU	48
D6.4	Case studies report	WP6	UGENT	Report	PU	45
D6.5	Inventory of RES4LIVE best practices	WP6	UNIBO	Report	PU	48
D7.1	Web Site and social media presence	WP7	EAAP	Websites, patents filling, etc.	PU	3
D7.2	RES4LIVE newsletter	WP7	EAAP	Websites, patents filling, etc.	PU	4
D7.3	RES4LIVE promotional material	WP7	CETRI	Websites, patents filling, etc.	PU	6
D7.4	Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR)	WP7	CETRI	Report	CO	8

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D7.5	RES4LIVE Best practices handbook	WP7	CETRI	Report	PU	48
D7.6	RES4LIVE final video	WP7	CETRI	Websites, patents filling, etc.	PU	48
D7.7	Report on scientific conferences, publications and final conference	WP7	EAAP	Report	PU	48
D7.8	First set of practice abstracts	WP7	EAAP	Report	PU	18
D7.9	Second set of practice abstracts	WP7	EAAP	Report	PU	48
D8.1	Project Management Handbook	WP8	AUA	Report	PU	3
D8.2	Data Management Plan & Support Pack	WP8	AUA	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	CO	6
D9.1	H - Requirement No. 1	WP9	AUA	Ethics	CO	6
D9.2	POPD - Requirement No. 2	WP9	AUA	Ethics	CO	6

Table 4: List of Deliverables (D)

The series of deliverables is given in a pert diagram in order to have a graphical overview of the workflow during the project (Figure 3).

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Figure 3: Deliverables Interrelation

Moreover, milestones are understood within the project as anchor points where technical decisions are taken, and work done so far is evaluated. Defined milestones are shown in the following Table.

List of Milestones (MS)					
MILESTONE No.	MILESTONE TITLE	WP No.	LEAD BENEFICIARY	DUE DATE (in months)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
MS1	Initial designs of heat pump, PVT system, and biogas upgrading kit	WP1	PSYCTOTHERM	9	The initial designs are finalized and confirm the expected performance and cost-related parameters/ Draft design report ready for internal use
MS2	The control algorithms of PLEGMA are compatible with the numerical tools of CERTH	WP3	CERTH	12	The coupling and software environment of these two numerical algorithms is agreed to enable their integration at a later stage

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MS3	Adapted Heat Pump manufactured	WP1	PSYCTOTHERM	18	Prototype heat pump designed based on the specifications of the Italian farm and manufactured by PSYCTO
MS4	Retrofit kit for tractor to be fuelled by biomethane developed	WP1	CRMT SAS	21	Tractor engine modifications and auxiliaries designed and methodology established/ D2.2 delivered
MS5	Smart control developed	WP3	PLEGMA LABS	24	Software-controller developed and trial runs (offline) conducted based on virtual conditions and data
MS6	Design of pilot systems finalized	WP4	ATB	27	The final design of all 4 pilot systems is concluded and preparations started
MS7	Numerical platform built-tested	WP3	CERTH	30	Simulation/optimization/tests/ D4.4 delivered
MS8	RES based systems installed at pilot farms and commissioned	WP4	ATB	33	The installed systems themselves/ D5.2 delivered
MS9	Real data of farms are available for conducting the case studies analysis	WP6	CERTH	39	Reliable data from 15 at least farms at different locations and types are available
MS10	Numerical platform validated	WP5	CERTH	45	Small deviation of the tools predictions compared to the test results on an annual basis / Draft D6.3 delivered
MS11	Outcomes of case studies analysis reveal high-impact solutions	WP6	UGENT	45	Integrated energy systems bring a large reduction of fossil fuels in a variety of farms and locations/ D7.4 delivered
MS12	De-fossilising targets set for pilot farms achieved	WP5	AUA	48	LCA and technical assessment results confirm the expectations/objectives

Table 5: List of Milestones (MS)

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3.2 Management Structure

The overall project management will be the responsibility of AUA, who will facilitate that all aspects of the project are well integrated. The overall aim of the project management is to ensure a good communication flow within but also outside the project, and to guarantee that the project will meet all objectives set on time, without budget deviations and with high quality results. Professional management of the project is ensured as well as its smooth and timely implementation; realize decision making as agreed in the Work Plan and in the Consortium Agreement (CA); facilitate the information flows and optimal coordination and collaboration among all project partners; implement the planned strategy for the dissemination of the project activities and results; reassuring that deliverables and milestones are of the expected quality and are completed on time, guarantee that administrative, financial, intellectual property and legal issues and compliance with EU priorities are fulfilled and address gender-related issues.

RES4LIVE partners will be bound by: (i) the Grant Agreement (GA) that depicts the rights and obligations towards the Commission, and (ii) the CA that details the rights and obligations between the contractual partners (the DESCA Model Consortium Agreement will be used as template for this reason). The main roles and instruments comprising the RES4LIVE project management structure is illustrated in Fig. 3.3 and presented next. RES4LIVE project management structure is presented in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Project Management Structure

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3.2.1 General Assembly (GA)

The General Assembly is the highest decision-making body of RES4LIVE, and its main role is to make decisions in crucial issues relevant to project entire progress. The General Assembly has the overall responsibility for decisions regarding the strategic orientation of the project (strategy, progress, major project revisions, collaboration with other projects, dissemination, etc.) as well as legal, financial and ethical issues, as detailed in the CA. Important tasks of the General Assembly are: supervision of the project and agreement on the work programme strategy; decision on all significant changes to work plans, WP structure and use of finances; decide on measures towards defaulting partners, etc.

It consists of one representative of each partner, is chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC), and meets on a semi-annual basis. The PC is responsible for the agenda and minutes of the meetings. If needed, telephone or video conferences will be organised in-between regular meetings. Additional meetings will also be organised on-demand or when critical decisions are needed. For details, refer to Table 8 of Annex 1.

3.2.2 Project Coordination Team (PCT)

The PCT consists of representatives of each organisation participating in the consortium and its main task will be project governance. It will have the overall responsibility of all technical, financial, legal, administrative, ethical, and dissemination issues of the project. It will monitor and assess the actual progress of the project and make amendments, where necessary. It will encompass the following main roles:

The Project Coordinator (PC) chairs the PCT and will be responsible for the overall management, communication, and coordination of the entire project. Special emphasis within his responsibilities will be to assure the overall integration of all WP activities. This role is assigned to Assistant Professor Dr.-Ing. Dimitris Manolakos (AUA) with an extensive experience on managing and working in EU projects for more than 15 years.

The Project Office (PO), which will coordinate management activities and will have expert secretarial, administrative, and technical support, supported by the Research Office of AUA, which is highly involved in H2020 projects. The PO will be chaired by the PC and will meet on a weekly basis throughout the project.

The Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (DEM), who will be responsible to raise public awareness of the project service, to ensure wide dissemination of the RES4LIVE results and share best practices, as well as for innovation management, IPR handling and the creation of the joint exploitation models and plan, and for supporting the partners in setting up their individual business plans, in order to exploit the results of the project. The DEM will also handle all IPR related issues, along with the guidance of the PC. This role is assigned to Mr. Thanos Karvounis (CETRI), with a large experience on similar activities in many successful EU projects.

The Risk and Quality Manager, the role of whom will be the early identification, assessment, and along with the support of the PC- the management of administrative and technical risks, as well as the development of the Quality Plan, the implementation of the quality procedures determined in it

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and the verification of the project results. This role is assigned to Dr. Stefano Benni (UNIBO), highly familiar with both the energy and livestock sectors.

3.2.3 Scientific and Technical Committee

Under the control and in compliance with the decisions of the PCT, the STC will be responsible for planning, execution and controlling of the project, with regards to issues of both scientific & technical nature. It shall be in charge of the project progress and will decide upon all relevant technical and administrative issues, such as: redirection of work in a WP, major transfer of resources across WPs or Partners (over 20%), technological choices, and changes in time plans. The STC will be composed by the Project Coordinator and the Work Package Leaders, who will be in charge of managing their WP as a self-contained entity. Their tasks include coordinating, monitoring and assessing the progress of the WP to ensure that output performance, costs and timelines are met.

3.2.3 International Advisory Board (IAB)

It will consist with up to 10 experts with worldwide reputation in the scientific and technical fields addressed by RES4LIVE and with complementary background. The IAB will offer high-end consultation services to the RES4LIVE consortium so as to ensure that the project's results will match the relevant community needs with the exact role and involvement to be defined in the first semester of the project. The IAB members will participate in specific consortium meetings so as to consult the partners about significant issues and decisions to be made. For details about the members so far are listed in Table 9 of Annex 1.

3.3 Contact with European Commission Services

3.3.1 Reporting to the Project Officer of the Commission

Reporting to the Commission is performed by the coordinator. It is based on: Deliverables, Mid-term Reviews and the Final Review.

SYGMA tool is used for reporting, allowing the upload of deliverables and other project related information. Continuous reporting module is activated at the time project starts, and it is always available for providing new information on the project. Coordinator can, at any time, upload deliverables and provide other information. Even if the coordinator is in charge of reporting, information from all partners will be requested before submission of all deliverables.

3.4 Website and Project Image

The domain "www.res4live.eu" has been purchased and a web page is being created. The website will be launched in December 2020 and will be constantly updated, including a public and a private section. The public section will include at least:

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- a) RES4LIVE description, prospects, news, events, and announcements
- b) RES4LIVE public documents available for download, including all project publications (complying with Open Access requirements); and
- c) links to other relevant sites, e.g. sites of partners and relevant EC sites

The private section will allow on-line collaboration between partners, including exchange of documents, exchange of messages in the form of e-mails and support for discussion lists, and a calendar with information about forthcoming events and tasks (workshops, meetings). Moreover, a logo is created as the image of the project, to be used both internally within the consortium and in all external communications related to the project. A project presentation is also created to be used by all project partners in the dissemination activities. This section of the document will be updated once website is available.

3.5 Collaboration Tools

Collaboration is the basis of the RES4LIVE project. The vast majority of partners have large and documented experience in collaborative projects, thus allowing an easy setup of collaboration procedures, crucial for the successful development of the project. The nature of this project is such that strong interaction between partners is required to achieve the expected results, as all activities are closely related, and teamwork is the catalyst of success.

Although self-control is assumed to be handled by each partner and within each WP, top level measures have been implemented, facilitating the collaboration process. The measures defined within next sections seem enough to conduct the project in an effective way.

3.5.1 Quality Assurance

The Coordinator has set an internal evaluation procedure for quality sustainability of deliverables. Each deliverable is assigned to a partner to deal with its preparation as lead participant (Table 4), but in order to achieve high quality result the following procedure is used:

- The deliverable lead partner will have to send out the first draft of the deliverable three (3) weeks before final submission to the Commission.
- The coordinator after inspecting the deliverable will send it to the partner assigned to internally evaluate it and provide a review by filling in a checklist (for the Deliverable's Review Template, refer to Annex 2).
- The assigned partner will have to finalise evaluation within a week to leave the deliverable leader enough time to correct the document, then s/he will send the reviewed document to the coordinator who will check the revision and transmit it to the deliverable lead partner for revision.
- The deliverable leader will send the final version to the Coordinator to read proof it and upload it to the SYGMA tool.

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3.5.2 Document Repository

A document repository will be set up in the project’s website, where all project documentation, including official documents, templates, meeting minutes, deliverables, will be inserted. The access to this server will be given through individual usernames and passwords, thus keeping detailed track of all modifications in different folders. The following folders will be created:

- Deliverables: contains separate subfolders per deliverable. This folder is just used to store already released versions of the deliverables.
- Official documents: separate subfolders are available for Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement, and project templates. Participants have read only access to this folder. Read-write access is reserved to the coordinator.
- Project meetings: contains separate subfolder per meeting, named “meeting description and location, date”. All information related to each meeting is stored here, including presentations given at the meeting.
- WPs: individual subfolders are created per WP. All information related to ongoing WPs is stored here, including working documents, non-released version of deliverables, etc.

Prior to the website’s launch, a MS Teams channel was created - accessible only to the Consortium members - to host all the necessary file and documents.

3.5.3 Contact and Mailing Lists

For each partner, the consortium has identified the names and contact details of¹: Main contact person(s), Financial contact person(s), and Communication - Dissemination Manager. For details, refer to Table 10 of the Annex 1.

3.6 Data Management

The European Commission promotes Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) research data to maximize the integrity and impact of their research investment. In this framework all partners will be responsible to ensure their research outputs will be organized so they can be more easily accessed, understood, exchanged and reused ensuring data security, accessibility and validation of results. Therefore, they will strive to make all their non-sensitive data available as green or gold open access in the form of journal publications, magazine articles etc. Besides, they want to ensure that the funding and regulatory body requirements are met, and that research data remain accurate, authentic, reliable and complete. A Data Management Plan (DMP) will be set up as part of a comprehensive research data management strategy which will minimize possible duplication of effort and the risk of data loss and will offer integrity to the data. As a result, research efficiency will increase, time and resources will be saved in the long term and compliance with practices conducted in industry and commerce will be achieved. Data generated will include large datasets on (1) test data for

¹ E-mail addresses, telephone numbers etc., have been circulated between Consortium members only.

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characterization mostly relevant to the heat pump, the PVT collector, and the tractor retrofitting, (2) numerical results of case studies simulations, and (3) test data of the energy systems from the pilot farms monitored over a long period.

The DMP will describe plans for creating, organizing, documenting, storing, and sharing data. It will take into account issues such as data protection and confidentiality (declaring which of the research data generated are open to public and which confidential), data preservation and curation, methodologies and standards applied, and will provide a framework that will support researchers and their data throughout the course of their research and beyond. It will be constantly updated describing what kind of research data will be generated, and what policies apply to the data. Funding and legal policies for data management practices such as backups, storage, access control, archiving will be determined. It will be clear who will own and have access to what data and who will be responsible for each aspect of the plan. Raw data and all other data generated during the project will be uploaded in an open repository (i.e. OpenAIRE), in order to contribute to the Open Access of scientific data within H2020. Moreover, partners will try to clearly describe which data will retain value after the end of the project, how their reuse will be enabled and how their long-term preservation will be ensured. Partners will share generated research data, allowing others to replicate, validate, or correct their results, thereby improving the scientific record. This will increase research integrity and replication as those who make use of their data and cite it in their own research will disseminate the results possibly in other disciplines, sectors, and countries. Moreover, in the future, partners will be able to identify, retrieve, and understand the data themselves after they have lost familiarity with it. Partners will not share specific parts of their research data if making them openly accessible would jeopardize the achievement of the project's main objectives. They will also not share data that they may not have the legal right to share because parts belong to other authors or entities.

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4 RISK MANAGEMENT

Given the dynamic nature of any project of this size and complexity, it is quite important, even from proposal

development stage, that the consortium has a well-defined risk management process and specific procedures to reassure early identification, adequate handling and proper mitigation of potential risks. In addition, another very important step is the pre-identification (well-before project start date) of the several types of risks that may potentially appear during project implementation, as well as the means to proactively handle and successfully address them so as to minimize potential uncertainties as much as possible.

Risk is defined as any event potentially precluding the achievement of the objectives of a certain activity or task. The Coordinator has the responsibility in terms of identification of the risks. Hence, when the first traces of possible risk show up, the Coordinator request from the respective WP leader to identify the risks relevant to their activity, or tasks, and properly document them to the GA and STC. Risk management requires identification, analysis, mitigation, control and application of contingency plans when risks materialize. It is a balance of judgment so that the risks are minimized without over-emphasizing the potential problems. For each risk identified in the course of the project, an exhaustive assessment shall be undertaken according to the following criteria:

- Risk identification: areas of potential risk will be identified and classified
- Risk quantification: the probability of events will be determined and the consequences associated with their occurrence will be examined
- Risk response: methods will be produced to reduce or control the risk
- Risk control and report: lessons learnt will be documented.

Risk Management will be the responsibility of the Risk and Quality Manager in terms of identification but the decision-making authority for major issues will remain with the PCT. Early detection and timely response to address any emerging issues will be crucial to effective risk management. In the event of technical changes, the PCT will task one or more WP Leaders to investigate the development and advise the PCT on appropriate actions.

Regarding the monitoring of risks identified, as well as updates, this will take place on an ad-hoc basis (when a new risk is identified) or once every six months. For every new major risk identified, the Project Coordination Committee will prepare a contingency plan to reassure the quality of project results and deliverables and the on-time execution of the project activities. All contingency plans will be incorporated to the overall organizational work plan of the project and will be further accompanied with partners' responsibilities to handle them. Finally, risks will be assessed separately and will be reported at least on semester basis in the project reports.

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Therefore, each risk will be analysed to determine its severity and probability of occurrence and a suitable procedure followed according to the type of risk. Mitigation actions will be defined in a case-by-case basis in order to avoid the risk or reduce the probability of occurrence. Contingency plans should be defined when a risk materialize in case of high severity/probability of the risk. The GA is the natural forum where contingencies are discussed and solved in most cases. The monitoring and reporting actions, depending on the quantification, are presented in the table below:

Risk Monitoring and Reporting Procedure	
QUANTIFICATION	MONITORING AND REPORTING ACTIONS
High/critical	Unacceptable risk: immediate detailed reporting to the Coordinator and immediate action initiation for risk mitigation and contingency plan. High frequency follow-up.
Medium	Unacceptable risk: immediate synthetic reporting to the Coordinator and action proposal for risk mitigation. Medium frequency follow-up.
Low/minor	Acceptable risk: no reporting and optional action proposal for risk mitigation. Low frequency follow-up.

Table 6: Risk Monitoring and Reporting Procedure

According to previous projects and experiences of the partners, some possible initial situations and healing actions have been identified. Our initial risk assessment has identified the major risks, which have been summarized hereinafter in Table 4.3. These descriptions include also the avoidance or mitigation strategies considered by the partners and WP leaders.

Critical Implementation Risks and Mitigation Actions			
RISK No.	RISK DESCRIPTION	WP No.	PROPOSED RISK MITIGATION MEASURES
1	Heat pump operating under the peculiar thermal loads of livestock buildings not achieving the COP target values. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP1 WP5	(i) In-depth evaluation of WP2 test data, for adjusting the internal control and reduce the temperature differences of heat source-supply. (ii) Feedback loop to WP2 to reconsider design parameters (e.g. size of key heat pump components). (iii) Adjust the heat supply design for coupling with the PVT (solar-assisted mode), for lifting up the COP.
2	Corrosive buildings environment erodes heat exchangers of heat pump. Level: Medium - Probability: Low	WP1 WP4	(i) Testing of other types of coating or heat exchanger materials (e.g. plastic) with higher corrosion resistance.

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			(ii) Re-evaluate heat transfer performance and adjust heat pump design.
3	The thermal energy produced by PVT exceeds the required thermal load during summer. Level: Low - Probability: Medium	WP1 WP4 WP5	An initial feasibility study has already been concluded for the pilot farms. An in-depth evaluation of the farms' needs will be conducted in WP4, focusing on the thermal load profile during the summer to ensure that the PVT matches the minimum heating needs and avoid oversizing.
4	Mismatch between electricity and thermal loads makes the sole application of PVT not feasible to fully cover both energy needs. Level: Low - Probability: High	WP5	(i) Adopting the option of hybrid PV and PVT systems. (ii) Case sensitive design according to the summer heat demand. (iii) Combine the PVT with heat pump with large water tanks for TES.
5	Biogas to biomethane upgrading system not cost-effective in small-/medium sized farms. Level: Medium - Probability: Medium	WP1 WP5	(i) Focus on adapting all components to lower sizes and finding market solutions of low price to also address small-medium-sized farms. (ii) Use the biomethane for variable uses (e.g. tractors, CHP units) to explore in WP6 the minimum farm size to make this technology competitive (as a function of local energy prices). (iii) Explore the food quality CO ₂ produced from a small/medium upgrading unit to add in the system cost-effectiveness.
6	Conversion kit for biomethane tractor engine requires major retrofitting to the engine and/or fitting only to the specific tractor type of the German pilot farm. Level: Low - Probability: Medium	WP1	CRMT will exploit its background knowledge of gas engine conversions for other engine types/ vehicles, which are executed with high accuracy and low risk. Moreover: (i) In case that major retrofits are needed for specific engine types, CRMT will focus on the tractor types that allow a low-cost retrofitting. (ii) Start collaboration with tractors' manufacturers for co-designing biomethane-fuelled tractors, either retrofitted or new.
7	Smart control deviates from the efficient/effective management of RES technologies. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP3	Experimental optimization based on data derived from the pilot farms in WP5. Feedback loops to Tasks 4.3-4.4 for improvements and real-time analysis and decision-making through ML methods.
8	Uncertainty of simulation/optimization results derived from numerical platform. Level: Medium - Probability: Medium	WP3 WP5	Numerical validation through: (1) available test data of individual components, and (2) pilot farms experimental data; re-arrangement of key technologies variables parameters.

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9	Uncertain cost-effectiveness of integrated energy systems. Level: High - Probability: Medium	WP1 WP2 WP3 WP5 WP6	(i) Emphasizing in co-design process in WP7, and reconsider design parameters to bring down the costs. (ii) Apply the tools of WP4 to maximize the economic benefits, probably reducing the fossil fuel savings to a range of 60-80%, instead of 100%, which is the maximum potential.
10	Data Confidentiality. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP8	During the implementation of pilots, participants may be unwilling to disclose sensitive operational information regarding environmental impacts of their activities. The Data Management Plan will effectively handle those issues, including the option for NDAs to be signed between RES4LIVE consortium and actors participating in pilots so as to ensure that all information given will be used only for the project purposes and no sensitive data will be made available to third parties.
11	Integrated RES systems are complex for the farmers to operate. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP4 WP5	Although not trivia, RES systems are built in the logic of O&M simplicity. Training of farm personnel will be done. One of the functions of the smart control is to fully take over the operation.
12	Access to GOLI commercial pilot farm/freedom to test. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP4	Tests may cause inconvenience in daily operations of farms. For that purpose, GOLI (commercial farm) is a consortium partner to secure his commitment and thus provide full access for testing purposes, always respecting the farm operations
13	Financial risk. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP8	Technical & scientific challenges and any uncertainty associated with RES4LIVE evolution can pose a significant impact on project costs. For this reason, administrative/financial management will not be limited to reporting, but it will also include a close financial monitoring so as to constantly assess financial progress and identify early signs of concern.
14	Changes in the project team. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP8	Changes will be identified as soon as possible. Partners will be required to include substitutes with equivalent (or higher) qualifications and experience and informed about their role and responsibilities.
15	Delay in the project timetable. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP8	The Consortium agrees on: (i) re-allocation of resources; (ii) parallel execution of tasks; or (iii) re-scheduling of activities or a suitable combination of those.

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16	Partners' withdrawal. Level: Low - Probability: Low	WP8	The consortium consists of well-known, experienced and professional partners, with many having strong collaboration between each other in the past. If a partner leaves then the replacement procedures initiate for substituting this member with an equivalent one from the wide network of the partners.
17	COVID-19. Level: Medium - Probability: High	WP8	In case of COVID-19 related confinement measures, all beneficiaries will immediately take all the necessary steps to limit any damage due to force majeure and do their best to resume implementation of the action as soon as possible. The consortium will foresee alternative activities in case the proposed activities will not be able to take place during the time scheduled.

Table 7: Critical Implementation Risks and Mitigation Actions

All beneficiaries will ensure that the deliverables are finalized in the due period; any necessary postponement of deliverables will be communicated to the Project Officer and approved by the REA.

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5 CONCLUSIONS

This document is the Project Management Handbook for the RES4LIVE project. Even if almost all descriptive information related to the project is included in the GA, this document summarizes the main important issues. Special emphasis has been given to the implementation of the project and the procedures required in order to ensure a successful finalization of the project, meeting all objectives and close to future commercialization. This is a live document that will be updated in case necessary.

Annex 1

General Assembly Members					
PARTNER No.	PARTNER ACRONYM	GENERAL ASSEMBLY MEMBER	PARTNER No.	PARTNER ACRONYM	GENERAL ASSEMBLY MEMBER
1	AUA	Dimitris Manolakos	10	PLEGMA LABS	Nikos Ipiotis
2	UNIBO	Stefano Benni	11	CRMT SAS	Olivier Marchand
3	ATB	Thomas Amon	12	TERRA	Hans Hoes
4	EV ILVO	Jarissa Maselyne	13	MG	João Gomes
5	UGENT	Steven Lecompte	14	CETRI	Thanos Karvounis
6	CERTH	Panagiotis Gremmelis	15	GOLINELLI	Giulio Golinell
7	AU	Guoqiang Zhang	16	EAAP	Riccardo Carelli
8	LVAT	Detlef May	17	EUREC	Greg Arrowsmith or Lourdes Laín Caviedes ²
9	PSYCTOTHERM	Pantelis Bakalis			

Table 8: General Assembly Members

International Advisory Board Members		
NAME	AFFILIATION AND COUNTRY	AREA OF EXPERTISE
Ing. Alessandro Guernelli	Studio Marconi 69, Italy	Architecture
Dr. Marco Alberghini	UGC - CISL Unione Generale Cultivatori di Bologna, Italy	Agriculture
Dr. Lorenzo Santi	Coldiretti - Confederazione Nazionale Coltivatori Diretti, Italy	Agriculture
Prof. Georgios Zervas	Agricultural University of Athens - Laboratory of Nutritional Physiology & Feeding	Livestock farming

Table 9: International Advisory Board Members

² Depending on availability.

	Document:	D8.1. Project Management Handbook		
	Author:	AUA	Version:	1
	Reference:	D8.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/12/20

Contact List			
ORGANIZATION	MAIN CONTACT	FINANCIAL ISSUES CONTACT	COMMUNICATION/DISSEMINATION MANAGER
AUA	Dimitris Manolakos and Dimitrios Tyris	Dimitris Manolakos and Vangelis Dimitriou	Vangelis Dimitriou
UNIBO	Stefano Benni	Luisella Sistu	Stefano Benni
ATB	Thomas Amon	Tobias Krüger	Barbara Amon
EV ILVO	Jarissa Maselyne	Jarissa Maselyne and Nancy Meersschaut	Cathy Plasman
UGENT	Steven Lecompte	Annick De Coster	Judith Ooms
CERTH	Athanasios Balafoutis	Matina Voulgaraki	Vasso Gavidou
AU	Li Rong	Li Rong	Li Rong
LVAT	Detlef May	Detlef May	Detlef May
PSYCTO	Pantelis Bakalis	Maria Monanterou	Maria Monanterou
PLEGMA	Stelios Kalogridis	Nikos Ipiotis	Stelios Kalogridis
CRMT SAS	Ronan Poupeau and Daniela Touze	Michelle Meillant	Daniela Touze
TERRA	Hans Hoes	Hans Hoes	Hans Hoes
MG	João Gomes	João Gomes	Manali Kulkarni
CETRI	Thanos Karvounis	Thanos Karvounis	Ioanna Barouni
GOLINELLI	Giulio Golinell	Giulio Golinell	Giulio Golinell
EAAP	Riccardo Carelli	Riccardo Carelli	Marlene Sciarretta
EUREC	Lourdes Laín Caviedes	Greg Arrowsmith	Lourdes Laín Caviedes

Table 10: Contact List

	Document:	D8.1. Project Management Handbook		
	Author:	AUA	Version:	1
	Reference:	D8.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/12/20

Annex 2

RES4LIVE

ENERGY SMART LIVESTOCK FARMING
TOWARDS ZERO FOSSIL FUEL CONSUMPTION

DELIVERABLE REVIEW TEMPLATE

REVIEW FACTSHEET

Deliverable no.	Deliverable X.X XXX
Responsible Partner (Name/Institution)	XXX
WP no. / Task no.	DX. XX / TX.XX
Version	X
Delivery Date	XX/XX/XX
Reviewer (Name/Institution)	
Review Date	

	Document:	D8.1. Project Management Handbook		
	Author:	AUA	Version:	1
	Reference:	D8.1 RES4LIVE ID GA 101000785	Date:	30/12/20

Review Checklist for RES4LIVE DX.XX

COMPLETENESS AND CORRECTNESS	ANSWER (Yes / No / Partly / N/A)	COMMENTS
Is the content of the deliverable adequate?		
Is there a clear statement of goals of the document?		
Are the key topics fully addressed?		
Are the results consistent with the goals?		
Are there any errors and/or contradictions?		
PRESENTATION	ANSWER (Yes / No / Partly / N/A)	COMMENTS
Is there an abstract?		
Is there a table of contents - if needed?		
Is there an index - if needed?		
Is the writing style clear?		
Are diagrams and/or pictures used where necessary?		
Do diagrams and/or pictures contain the necessary amount of information?		
Is terminology consistent throughout the documents?		
Does terminology conform to (scientific field's) standards?		
Is the document adequately supplied with references?		
Are there references of related publications, which may contain further information?		
Are the references in alphabetical order and complete enough to locate the original publications?		

OVERALL REMARKS AND SUGGESTIONS:

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